

ORIGINAL UNIQUENESS THEOREM FOR FUNCTIONS WITH MATRIX

ARGUMENTS

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Abstract. In this paper, we summarize the original uniqueness theorem for functions of matrix arguments. As in any theory, the Unity Theorem is important in operational calculus. Therefore, the uniqueness theorem for functions with matrix arguments is introduced, which later helps us to introduce other theorems.

Keywords. Laplace transform, Complex symmetric matrix, matrix original function, matrix image function.

Definition. Let $f(A)$ be a function of $A > 0 (A \in \square [m \times m])$ and $Z = X + iY$, be a $(Z \in \square [m \times m])$ complex symmetric matrix. The Laplace transform $F(Z)$ of $f(A)$ defined as

$$F(Z) = \int_{A>0} \exp(-ZA) f(A) dA. \quad (1)$$

Where the integral is assumed to be absolutely convergent in the right half plane $\text{Re}(Z) = X > X_0 > 0$. Determined by formula (1) the function $f(A)$ is the matrix image function of the matrix original function $f(A)$. The original and image are defined as: $f(A) \xleftarrow{\bullet} F(Z)$ or $F(Z) \xrightarrow{\bullet} f(A)$. (The " $\xleftarrow{\bullet}$ " sign is always oriented to the original.)

The Laplace transform $F(Z)$ of $f(A)$ defined above is an analytic function of Z in the right half plane $\text{Re}(Z) = X > X_0 > 0$. In addition, if

$$\int_{-\infty < Y = Y' < \infty} |F(X + iY)| dY < \infty \quad (2)$$

for all $X > X_0 > 0$, and

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow 0} \int |F(X + iY)| dY = 0$$

then the unique inverse Laplace transform $f(A)$ of $F(Z)$ is

$$f(A) = \frac{2^{\frac{1}{2}m(m-1)}}{(2\pi i)^{\frac{1}{2}m(m+1)}} \int_{\text{Re}(Z)=X>X_0>0} \exp(ZA) F(Z) dZ \quad (3)$$

The function $f(A)$ defined by formula (3) is a matrix original function of the matrix $F(Z)$ image function.

Below we present the original uniqueness theorem, which is very important for operational calculus.

Theorem (*the original uniqueness theorem*). If the function $F(Z)$

function two $f_1(A)$ and $f_2(A)$ is the image function of the originals, then this

the originals overlap at all their points of continuity. That is, $f_1(A) = f_2(A)$.

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